

BACTERIOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF SOME NIGERIAN LOCAL FOOD DRINKS
(Kunnu-zaki, Yogurt and Zobo)

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ABSTRACT

Three types of African food drinks ((Kunnu-zaki (or simply Kunnu), Yogurt and Zobo)) were analysed for their bacteria characteristics including their antibiotic sensitivity. The total colony forming units was analysed using the spread plate method for the food drinks. Ten isolates were selected at random from each of the food drinks and tentatively identified in which the following cumulative genera of bacteria occurred: *E.coli* 10 (33.3)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 10 (33.3), *Staphylococcus species* 6 (20), and *Streptococcus species* 4(13.3). For Kunnu, out of 10 identified isolates: *E.coli* 5 (50)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 2 (20), and *Staphylococcus species* 3 (33.3). In the case of Yogurt, out of 10 identified isolates: *E.coli* 3 (30)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 5 (50) and *Enterococcus species* 2 (20). For Zobo, out of 10 identified isolates: *E.coli* 2 (20)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 3 (30), and *Staphylococcus species* 3 (30). Indication was that there was significant difference in the TCFU ml⁻¹ of the food drinks (P= 0.004); ranging from 6.10E+06 to 4.23E+06 in which Kunnu was highest while Zobo was least impacted. The results of the sensitivity tests on the *E.coli*. isolates indicated resistance to: Nitrofurantoin, Chloramphenicol, Cefuroxime and Ampicillin; Norfloxacin and Gentamicin were partially resistance while Ciprofloxacin, Tetracycline, Amoxicillin and Ofloxacin indicated sensitivity on *E.coli*. Also, while the drink Kunnu had two of the three *Staphylococcus* sp to be both tube/slide coagulase positive; Zobo had only one of the three isolates to be positive, while no *Staphylococcus* sp were isolated from Yogurt. The objective of the paper was therefore to conduct an investigation on the characteristics of the bacteria isolates in the drinks, especially the presence of probable veritable pathogens.

(*) Numbers in parenthesis represent percentages

KEYWORDS: *Kunnu-zaki, yogurt, zobo, food drinks, microbiological quality, coagulase test.*

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INTRODUCTION

Locally processed food drinks are taken as refreshment in-between meals, and also along with meals. They are usually considered non alcoholic beverages. Examples that are sold in Nigeria are *Kunnu, Yogurt and Zobo*. In Nigeria, the sale and consumption of these local food drinks are not regulated due to their low cost in comparison to industrially manufactured soft drinks. Moreover as they are patronised mostly by low income earners or persons who appreciate their exotic tastes. In developing nations like Nigeria, there is likely to be a high risk of chemical and microbial contamination due to lack of appropriate legislation. The state of hygiene of the food drinks is suspect due largely to much handling; use of doubtful water quality during processing, non-hygienic packaging and storage environments. Previous study on local food drinks have been carried out. In 2006, Osotimehin et al, carried out a

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pilot study on Kunnu for Increasing the Market Acceptance of Local Food Drinks Through Concept - Testing: The results of the study suggested that the drink might enjoy a higher level of patronage if it is reformulated, as well as hygienically processed and appropriately packaged. They suggested that processors of the drink be exposed to some form of training to enhance their skill. Also, Adeleke and Abiodun, 2010, studied the physico-chemical properties of commercial local beverages in Osun State, Nigeria; indication was that the titratable acidity and ascorbic acid of zobo and pito were not feasible due to the products colour while the high alcoholic content of ogogoro, burukutu and palmwine signifies that the products can cause health problem such as obesity and can damage the organs in the body. The present study was designed to investigate the characteristics of the bacteria isolates in the drinks, especially for the presence of probable veritable pathogens.

African local food drinks

Food drinks are liquid pasty foods often made from cereals, milk and/or other parts of plants. These drinks could be non-fermented or fermented. They are usually consumed by children and adults; especially by students and the working class as cooling- off drinks during hot afternoons. These drinks are consumed anytime of the day and they are usually used as appetizer to entertain visitors in rural and urban centres and could be served at social gatherings (Amusa and Odunbaku, 2009). In Amassoma, Bayelsa state, where this study was carried out, these food drinks were sold in different market places at any given time of the day.

Kunnu (KU)

This is a traditional non alcoholic fermented beverage which is consumed mostly in the northern parts of Nigeria especially during the dry season. Kunnu drink is prepared from millet by cleaning the seeds and soaking in water for about two hours. The soaked seeds are later wet-milled and the slurry sieved with a muslin cloth. The filtrate is allowed to ferment for a day, during which the slurry settles and form sediments. The supernatant liquid is decanted, and the residue mixed with water and divided into two. Half the residue is boiled and the second half poured into it to produce Kunnu (Sowonola et al., 2005). The resultant beverage has low viscosity with a sweet-sour taste, milky cream appearance, and is popular with people in the northern parts of Nigeria. Kunnu is consumed mainly by people within the low income class. Red pepper, which is added to this drink, is rich in nutrients that prevent cancer (Shimizu and Weinstein, 2005).

Yogurt (YO)

Yogurt or yoghurt or yoghourt is a fermented milk product (soy milk, nut milks such as almond milk, and coconut milk can also be used) produced by bacterial fermentation of milk. The bacteria used to make yogurt are known as "yogurt cultures". Fermentation of lactose by these bacteria produces lactic acid, which acts on milk protein to give yogurt its texture and its characteristic taste. The milk is first heated to about 80 °C (176 °F) to kill any undesirable bacteria and to denature the milk proteins so that they set together rather than form curds. In some places, such as parts of India, curds are a desired component and milk is not pasteurized but boiled. The milk is then cooled to about 45 °C (112 °F). The bacterial starter-culture is added, and the temperature is maintained for 4 to 7 hours to allow fermentation. Yogurt is known to be rich in protein, calcium, riboflavin, vitamin B6 and B12 and contains live cultures which are claimed to prevent diarrhoea (Ripudaman et al., 2003).

Zobo (ZO)

Zobo is also a non alcoholic local beverage made from different varieties of dry petals of the plant *Hibiscus sabdariffa*. Dried roselle calyces were washed and soaked overnight in distilled water (1:10 w/v). This was boiled for 15 min and filtered while still hot. Different fruits: apples, oranges and pineapples (about 400 g, respectively) were also separately washed, peeled and cut (seeds removed). The fruits were blended in a warring blended and filtered. The extract from the roselle calyces was mixed with the filtrate of each fruit (i.e. apples, oranges and pineapples) at three different ratios (1:1 w/v), (1:2 w/v) and (1:3 w/v), respectively and sugar added to each drink (1:20 w/v). The produced drinks include: Roselle-apple drink, Roselle-orange and Roselle-pineapple drink. The drinks were pasteurized at 95°C for 5 min, cooled and packaged in clean uniform plastic bottles. Zobo drink is recommended for hypertensive patients and also serve as a good cure for diarrhoea and pneumonia. The drink has

been recommended for the control of cholesterol levels in the blood and in the prevention of bladder infection and constipation (Fasoyiro *et al*, 2005).

Food sanitary quality

The locations from which the food drinks were bought had high density of human population. The drinks were hawked about bottled with unprotected stoppers by the young and adult sellers. The contamination of water and foods with pathogens had been known for centuries (Pandey, 2007). Diseases such as brucellosis, typhoid fever, diphtheria and tuberculosis have been associated with poor pasteurization of milk and other foods. Food contamination through much handling has been much studied. The sanitary quality of food is usually determined by the presence or absence of potential pathogens or by the low microbial counts per gram of the food. In general however, the content of certain indicator organisms is used for determining the sanitary quality of foods (Kigigha and Uge, 2012). According to Isara *et al*. (2010) the prevalence of food contamination in the fast food restaurants in Benin in Nigeria, was found to be 37.5%. In which *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were the most commonly isolated bacteria, while salads, meat pie and fried rice were the most commonly contaminated foods.

The indicator organisms presently used for food quality assessment include, Coliform and the *Enterococci*. In the examination of foods and water, the presence of *Enterobacteria* indicated the level of cleanliness while the presence of pathogens indicated the safety level of the food. A tentative standard using the Coliform (*Escherichia coli* count) which applies to some foods indicated that for a grade A milk, 10 ml^{-1} ; for pre-cooked/partially cooked frozen foods 10 g^{-1} ; while for crab-meat and pastry foods such as custard (and probably the food drinks) 100 g^{-1} could be acceptable limits. For frozen foods in particular, the use of the *Enterococcus* index for food safety had been advocated (Jay, 2005).

Infection from food handling

The preponderance of *Staphylococcus aureus* in foods has been used as an indication of much handling; while the presences of *Bacillus* and other Gram-positive rods has been used to infer contamination from soil and environment. Penicillinase (or B-lactamase) which occurs also in *S.aureus* is able to degrade the antibiotic, penicillin; similarly, deoxyribonuclease (or DNase) hydrolyses deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) (Cheesbrough, 2006). One important attribute of the pathogenic *S.aureus* is the ability to coagulate blood plasma through the conversion of fibrinogen to fibrin. The coagulase enzyme is found in the coagulase positive *S.aureus* while the coagulase negative strains lack it. Conversion of fibrinogen is in two forms viz. the free coagulase which acts by converting fibrinogen to fibrin by activating a coagulase- reactor in plasma while the bound coagulase or clump-factor converts fibrinogen to fibrin directly without requiring a coagulase – reactor. The former can be detected by the rapid slide test, and the later by the tube test (Cheesbrough, 2006). The formation of clot or fibrin, interferes with the functioning of the phagocytes through the deposition of fibrin on their surfaces thereby encasing them and causing them to be anti-phagocytic. In recent times, the presence of *Enterococcus faecalis* has been used to infer faecal contamination. The *Enterococcus* sp has been much studied with respect to their ability to transfer resistance factors among the *Micrococcaceae*.

Antibiotic sensitivity test of Escherichia sp

The emergence of antibiotic resistant bacteria is a common occurrence. Antibiotic treatment may select for bacterial strains with physiological or genetically enhanced capacity to survive high doses of antibiotics. Under certain conditions, it may result in preferential growth of bacteria while growth of susceptible bacteria is inhibited by the drug. Antibiotic resistance genes can be exchanged between different bacterial strains or species via plasmids that carry these resistance genes. Antibiotics resistance results from a number of causes viz. through misuse by health professionals; from overuse in treating human diseases; their use as growth promoters in animal foods; their availability over the counter without prescription; patient failure to follow prescribed course of treatment and from patients stopping therapy when they feel better but still have an active bacterial infection (Witte, 2004).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Soft drink samples.

Locally processed food drinks samples viz. Kunnu (KU), Yogurt (YO) and Zobo (ZO) were bought from Amassoma market in Bayelsa State of Nigeria. They were conveyed to the laboratory within the hour and stored in the refrigerator for the study.

Reagents and media

All the glass-wares used were washed thoroughly and rinsed three times with distilled and de-ionized water and autoclaved for 15 minutes at 121°C. All reagents were prepared according to manufacturers specifications and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 min except for the sugar solutions which were sterilized by tyndalization.

Enumeration of microbial load of leaf samples.

One millilitre of each of the food drink samples (Kunnu, Yogurt and Zobo), were subjected to ten-fold serial dilution using normal saline. Spread plates in triplicates were made on Nutrient Agar using 0.1 ml from the dilutions from the 6th ten-fold serial dilution tubes and colonies counted after incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The TCFU ml⁻¹ of the food drinks were determined in triplicates.

Isolation and identification of representative bacteria forms.

Ten representative morphologically different bacterial forms from spread plate culture of the food drinks, were randomly isolated and stored in Agar slants at 5°C for further identification. Further tests to identify the bacterial forms included growth on Kligler Iron Agar (KIA); Citrate utilization test for characterization of the *Enterobacteriaceae* and the Urease test for the identification of the *Proteus* sp. Indole test was carried out using organisms sub-cultured in peptone water and testing with Kovac's reagent (p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde). Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) was used as a differential and selective medium for the isolation of *S. aureus* and the Catalase test for distinguishing Catalase and non-catalase producing bacteria. *S. aureus* isolates were further tested for bound and free Coagulase using the Tube and Slide Coagulase tests (Cheesbrough, 2006).

RESULTS

Figure 1: Shows the results on the TCFU bacteria of food drinks. The drink samples were divided into three. Indication was that the mean values of the three food drink samples when compared showed significant differences ($P= 0.004$); ranging from $6.10E+06$ to $4.23E+06$. Pair-wise comparisons for factors (or Tukey test), showed that there is much difference between Kunnu and Zobo drinks, Kunnu and Yogurt drinks with respect to their TCFU ml⁻¹; there was no difference between yogurt and zobo drinks. Ten isolates were selected at random from each of the food drinks and tentatively identified as shown in Table 1. The following cumulative genera of bacteria occurred: *E.coli* 10 (33.3)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 10 (33.3), *Staphylococcus species* 6 (20), and *Streptococcus species* 4(13.3). For Kunnu, out of 10 identified isolates: *E.coli* 5 (50)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 2 (20), and *Staphylococcus species* 3 (33.3). In the case of Yogurt, out of 10 identified isolates: *E.coli* 3 (30)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 5 (50) and *Streptococcus species* 2 (20). For Zobo, out of 10 identified isolates: *E.coli* 2 (20)*, *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods 3 (30), and *Staphylococcus species* 3 (30). (* numbers in parenthesis represent percentages). In Table 2, the results of the sensitivity tests on the *E.coli*. isolates indicated resistance to: Nitrofurantoin, Chloramphenicol, Cefuroxime and Ampicillin; Norfloxacin and Gentamicin were partially resistance while Ciprofloxacin, Tetracycline, Amoxicillin and Ofloxacin indicated sensitivity on *E.coli*. Also, while the drink Kunnu had two of the three *Staphylococcus* sp to be both tube/slide coagulase positive; Zobo had only one of the three isolates to be positive, while no *Staphylococcus* sp were isolated from Yogurt. Numbers in parenthesis (*) represent percentages.

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Fig 1: TCFU ml⁻¹ of food drinks. In which YO = Yogurt; KU = Kunnu and ZO = Zobo. Data = mean ($\pm$ S. E.; n=3); (P= 0.004).

Table1: Characterisation of bacteria isolates from Local Food Drinks

BACTERIA ISOLATES / TESTS	I	II	III	V
Colonial morphology	Golden/ entire	Whitish/dry entire	Creamy / entire	Mucoid/ entire
Gram's reaction	+ve cocci in clusters	+ve rods in chains	+ve cocci in chains	-ve rods
Growth on MSA	+ve	NT	-ve	NT
Tube Coag.	+ve	NT	-ve	NT
Slide Coag.	+ve	NT	-ve	NT
Litmus test	-ve	NT	+ve	NT
Oxidase test	NT	NT	-ve	-ve
Citrate	NT	NT	NT	-ve
Sugar Use:	NT	NT	NT	
Lactose				+ve
Mannitol				+ve
Glucose				+ve
Sucrose				+ve
Growth in KIA:	NT	NT	NT	
-Acid/Gas				+ve
-H ₂ S				-ve
-Butt /Slope				Y/Y
Tentative identification	<i>Staph. sp</i>	<i>Bacil</i> & other G +ve rods	<i>Entero . sp</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
KU	3 (2)**	2	0	5
YO	0	5	2	3
ZO	3 (1)	3	2	2
Cumulative CFUml ⁻¹ from Food drinks	6 (20.0)*	10 (33.3)	4 (13.3)	10 (33.3)

(*) Numbers in parenthesis represent percentages;

(**) Numbers in parenthesis represent tube/slide coagulase positive;

Staph. sp = *Staphylococcus* species; *Bacillus* & other G +ve rods = *Bacillus* and other Gram positive rods; *Entero. spp* = *Enterococcus* spp; *E.coli* = *Escherichia* sp. YO = Yogurt; KU = Kunnu and ZO = Zobo.

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Table 2: Antibiotic sensitivity test of *Escherichia* sp.

ISOLATES (<i>E.coli</i>)	KU 4	KU 5	KU 6	KU 7	KU 9	YO 1	YO 7	ZO 3
NITROFURATION	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
CIPROFLOXACIN	++	+++	++	++	+++	++	+++	++
TETRACYCLINE	++	+	+	++	+	+	++	+
NORFLOXACIN	+	+	+	+	++	R	+	R
AMOXYCLINE	+	+	+	++	++	+	+	+
OFLOXACIN	++	++	++	++	+++	+	++	++
CHLORAMPHENICOL	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
CEFUROXIME	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
AMPLICILLIN	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
GENTAMICIN	+	+	R	+	+	R	+	R

KEYS:

Slightly Sensitive: +

Moderately Sensitive: ++

Widely Sensitive: +++

Resistance: R

YO = Yogurt; KU = Kunnu and ZO = Zobo.

DISCUSSION

Of the three types of African food drinks that were microbiologically characterised, Kunnu appears to be more infected with potential pathogens in number and type. In which Kunnu was highest in the TCFU ml⁻¹, while Zobo was least impacted (P = 0.004). From the point of view of coagulase positivity and presence of indicator organisms, which are known indicators of pathogenicity (Kigigha and Uge, 2012; Isara et al. 2010; Witte, 2004), Kunnu had 5 of the isolates as *E.coli* in which all the isolates were resistant to the antibiotics: Nitrofurantoin, Chloramphenicol, Cefuroxime and Ampicillin. For Yogurt and Zobo, only two and one *E.coli* isolates respectively were identified and they were resistant also to the above mentioned antibiotics. Of the three *S.aures* isolated from Kunnu, two were coagulase positive while only one of the three isolates in Zobo showed positivity; there were no *S.aureus* isolates in Yogurt. In this era of widespread antibiotic usage and the attendant development of drug resistance, the presence of the *Enterococcus* spp is of grave importance (Klare et al, 2003; Seema et al, 2008). Indication was that Kunnu and Yogurt were incriminated in the possible proliferation of the *Enterococcus* spp while Zobo did not indicate their presence.

In conclusion, the local production of foods and drinks in Nigeria has for decades been left entirely in the hands of local producers without appropriate regulation and legislation even though handling procedure, quality of water used and the state of hygiene of the environment and of the producers remain very suspicious. The study demonstrated the need to recommend on some form of control in the production procedure, packaging and storage in the local food industry. For example, in the production of Kunnu, the addition of half of the 2 hour soaked and milled grains without some form of sterilization could easily be implicated in the number and type of isolates from the food drink (Sowonola et al., 2005).

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